
Digital Transformation in Education at Thu Dau Mot University

Trinh Huynh Chan

Thu Dau Mot University

ABSTRACT: In an era of rapid scientific and technical development, universities that want to survive and develop must always innovate and update scientific and technical advances in all activities of their units. Digital transformation is one of the practical activities to improve the quality and operations of universities. At Thu Dau Mot University, digital transformation is an issue that the school is very interested in and developing. In this article, the author focuses on understanding and analyzing the current state of digital transformation at Thu Dau Mot University campus, finding the causes and limitations that need to be overcome.

KEYWORDS: Digital transformation, digital technology, Thu Dau Mot University, education, teaching and learning.

1. INTRODUCTION

The 21st century is called the digital era, when science and technology develops rapidly, every field is affected by the rapid development and change of information and communication technology (Balyerand Oz, 2018). With the very strong development of the 4.0 revolution, digital transformation is an inevitable trend in today's era. Thanks to the artificial intelligence (AI) platform, cloud computing (icloud), big data (Big Data), Internet of things along with countless software and applications that are born every day, digital transformation happening fast and strong all over the world. This is an opportunity for countries and businesses to develop, but it is also a risk of falling behind and being left further and further behind for countries and businesses that are not interested in digital transformation. Digital transformation is not simply a higher level of application and development of information and communications technology but a breakthrough in socio-economic development (Ngan, 2021).

In Vietnam, digital transformation is taking place at a rapid pace and is considered one of the Government's top priorities (Loan, Tham, 2024). In the field of education, the Government's attention must include the National Digital Transformation Program, approved by the Prime Minister in 2020: "Developing a platform to support remote teaching and learning, thoroughly applying digital technology in management, teaching and learning; digitize documents and textbooks; Build a platform to share teaching and learning resources in both face-to-face and online forms. Developing technology to serve education, towards individualized training. 100% of educational institutions deploy remote teaching and learning, including testing training programs that allow students to learn online at least 20% of the program content. Applying digital technology to assign homework and check students' preparation before going to class" (Prime Minister, 2020); or the project on enhancing the application of information technology and digital transformation in education and training for the period 2022 - 2025, with a vision to 2030: "Taking advantage of technological advances to promote innovation in teaching and learning." learning, improving the quality and opportunities to access education, and effective educational management; building an open, adaptive education on a digital platform, contributing to the development of digital government, digital economy and digital society." The goal by 2025 is to "Strongly innovate the way of organizing education, making teaching and learning in the digital environment an essential, daily educational activity for every teacher and every learner" (Prime Minister government, 2022).

With the attention of the Government, the education sector as well as local authorities pay great attention to investing in the development of this field. However, digital transformation involves machinery, tools, facilities, etc. (related to funding), so development is not uniform among localities. In Binh Duong - one of the provinces with a relatively solid economic development, digital transformation in education in particular and in other socio-economic fields in general is relatively favorable, creating favorable conditions for the economy. Education development meets the trends of the times.

Thu Dau Mot University - the only public university in the province, with the mission of training quality human resources to serve the socio-economic development and international integration of Binh Duong province, Southeast region Ministry - Southern key economic region and become a research consulting center in the region. After nearly 15 years of establishment and development, the School has shaped itself into a multi-disciplinary and multi-field educational institution; developed according to the advanced university model. With the philosophy "Aspiration - Responsibility - Creativity", the School has been affirming its position as a high-quality training and scientific research unit, a typical representative of the province's intellectual strength. Binh Duong (Thu

Digital Transformation in Education at Thu Dau Mot University

Dau Mot University, 2023). Digital transformation is one of the important activities in the School's activities, a strategic goal to increase value, towards strong development.

2. RESEARCH OVERVIEW AND RESEARCH METHODS

The issue of digital transformation in general and digital transformation in education in particular, although not new, is still a relatively unfamiliar concept to some people. In this article, based on theoretical research, focusing on collecting, analyzing and synthesizing documents to gain an overview of digital transformation and digital transformation in education, the author then searches and compiles Combine reports, data, and official dispatches related to digital transformation at Thu Dau Mot University, combined with the actual teaching and activities of individuals at Thu Dau Mot University to write up the current status of digital transformation. at Thu Dau Mot University.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. Digital conversion

Digital transformation is a topic that many researchers are interested in, and therefore many definitions have been proposed about it. Bill Schmarzo (2017) defined: "Digital transformation is the application of digital capabilities to processes, products and assets to improve efficiency, enhance customer value, manage risks and explore unlock new money-making opportunities. Siebel defines "The nature of digital transformation is the convergence of four breakthrough technologies: cloud computing technology, big data, internet of things (IoT) and artificial intelligence." create (AI)". The Enterprise Project website defines "Digital transformation is the integration of digital technology into all areas of a business, fundamentally changing the way it operates and brings value to customers. It is also a cultural change, requiring organizations to continually challenge the status quo, experiment and be comfortable with failure." In Vietnam, according to Pham Huy Giao (2020) "Digital transformation is the use of digital technology or the application of digital technology on the basis of digital data or digitized data to change research and production models." production and business to create new opportunities and values, improve and enhance operational efficiency and competitiveness of organizations/agencies/enterprises".

So it can be understood: Digital transformation (Digital Transformation) is the process of converting traditional information, services, products, activities and processes into digital form, or digital technology. It includes the use of digital technology, such as computers, internet, artificial intelligence, big data, other digital technologies to improve and optimize various aspects of life and business operations.

Digital transformation technology is developing very strongly in today's era, it was born in the era of internet explosion. Therefore, it is changing people's lives every day, affecting many aspects of social activities.

+ In business: Businesses use digital transformation to improve management, production processes, marketing, and customer service. Digital transformation can help businesses improve performance and create new business models.

+ In education: Digital transformation in education can include the use of online learning platforms (Microsoft Teams, Zoom, Google Meet, ...), educational applications (Powerpoint, Canva myViewBoard, ...), online courses to improve the learning and teaching process.

+ In healthcare: The healthcare industry uses digital technology to manage medical records, create appointments, online consultation, and monitor personal health, ...

+ In traffic: Digital technology helps improvetraffic system through mobile phone applications, navigation systems, and real-time traffic information.

+ Government: Use digital technology to provide online public services, manage population data, and create applications for the community.

As such, digital transformation plays an important role in many fields, creating convenience and efficiency but also creating new opportunities and changing the way people interact with the world around them. At the same time, it often comes with information security and privacy challenges, and requires training and specialization to take advantage of the full potential of digital technology.

3.2. Digital transformation in education

Society develops, economy develops, so training people needs to be one step ahead. Digital transformation has changed the entire landscape of socio-economic development, education cannot be indifferent to this change (Balyerand Oz, 2018).

Today we are living in the information age, with multi-dimensional changes in the structure of individuals and society. With the growing popularity of knowledge, teaching and learning activities begin to diverge from traditional approaches (Bozkurt, 2015). Information and communication technology is developing rapidly, and the use of digital tools in educational environments is also increasing (Parlak, 2017). The changes taking place in the information age, the impacts of globalization and technology, require changes and improvements in educational systems, approaches and processes, requiring transformational development. digital transformation to understand, adapt, and design our educational system, which is still dominated by classical understanding, relevant to today's conditions (Parlak, 2017).

Digital Transformation in Education at Thu Dau Mot University

In the context of the development of information and communication technologies, education can not only take place outside the school environment but also become an indispensable part of everyday life (Şişman, 2016). Currently, with the elimination of information and knowledge "border" barriers globally through fiber optic technology, not only the form and content but also the methods of education and learning are undergoing changes. change significantly. Instead of a teacher-centered focus, a move toward placing students at the center of the learning process has become part of these changes. Furthermore, distance education, computer-assisted learning, e-learning, virtual learning environments, and other emerging technologies are clear evidence that education is experiencing new aspects in the era of digital transformation.

So what is digital transformation in education?: "TransformationDigital in education is the application of digital technology and internet information systems in the field of education to improve the quality of teaching, learning and educational management. Including improving teaching methods, improving equipment and learning aids, enhancing the experience of students and training participants" (Pace institute of management).

Thus, digital transformation in education focuses on two aspects:

+ Teaching methods,

+ Learning support equipment and tools.

Learning support equipment and tools are physical products, tools to support education in digital transformation, and are related to funding. Meanwhile, the teaching method is a factor that is subjectively determined by people. Teachers, if they are aware that teaching methods are a decisive factor in the development of education, will make efforts to change to suit the requirements of the times. In one of his studies, OECD (2018) also placed high value on methodological change: adjusting teaching methods to equip students with the necessary skills to build a more inclusive, cohesive and effective society. . Agreeing on the viewpoint of changing methods to practice skills in the era of digital transformation, Peterson and colleagues (2018) said that: innovation in teaching methods to encourage students to actively participate in the process learning process, thereby developing the skills and attitudes necessary for the learning journey. Skill development should not only focus on students but also on teachers through methods such as raising problems or project methods, etc. Changing methods will help students apply knowledge. into new situations in a world of continuous change and rapid evolution (OECD, 2018). To do this, education needs to adapt to provide students with the skills necessary to build a more equitable and productive society. Under these conditions, schools need to provide learning in hard skills such as technology design and resource management, as well as soft skills such as communication, empathy and social awareness, thereby helping students participate in building inclusive and equitable societies (WEF, 2020). These skills are essential to help people progress in an increasingly complex, interconnected and rapidly changing world (OECD, 2019). Students who are better prepared for the future will be able to become positive agents, understand and empathize with the intentions and emotions of others, and be aware of short-term and long-term consequences of issues affecting society (OECD, 2018). Therefore, as Schleicher (2016) pointed out, teachers need to use digital technology in the teaching process and must understand the rapid development of digital knowledge, skills and technology.

Thus, digital transformation is reshaping the traditional way of education to a new education system, with many changes in form and quality.

+ Traditional education with the classroom model, with neat rows of desks, white chalk - blackboards, lessons set in books, ... education in the digital age has changed this model, creating a flexible learning space: learners can study and acquire knowledge anytime, anywhere, with devices connected to the internet such as computers, laptops, phones, iPads, etc. Learners can It is possible to completely eliminate limitations on age, geographical space distance, and optimize study time, thereby easily creating a learning society.

+ Teachers and learners can easily exchange and share information and knowledge with each other through the internet space. Through cyberspace, learners and teachers can easily find many sources of information and extensive and in-depth knowledge. In addition, digital transformation is a huge open source of learning materials for learners.

+ The application of digital technology will help learners have comfortable study time, anytime, anywhere; Find information easily, ... bring initiative in learning.

+ Teachers can easily improve their teaching effectiveness through the application of teaching software, such as Power point, Prezi, Flipgrid... Besides, teachers can also easily use teaching support tools advanced, bringing human knowledge into its lectures with vivid images and videos. With 4.0 technology, learners can experience multi-sensory experiences, creating a feeling of curiosity and more excitement when learning.

+ The application of digital technology in education will bring efficiency, such as Bigdata will help store knowledge from basic to in-depth; IoT will accurately track the activities of teachers, students and administrators; Blockchain will fully manage information, clear student education records, accurate records of learning history as well as transparent transcripts,...

+ Digital transformation will help save costs in education. Digital transformation creates many choices for learners: instead of going to school or class, they can participate in E-learning courses at many times cheaper costs (no money for premises or facilities). facilities, equipment, ...); Learners can even choose courses that suit them and the topics/topics they are really interested in.

Digital Transformation in Education at Thu Dau Mot University

Vietnam is implementing digital transformation in the education sector through many important measures and policies. These innovations are creating huge and positive change. The Government has determined that developing facilities to support distance teaching and learning, using digital technology in management, teaching, and learning, digitizing documents and textbooks, and building a sharing platform Sharing teaching and learning resources, both in-person and online, plays an important role in shaping the future of education. The goal is to develop technology for education and promote personalized training.

Vietnam has implemented many policies to support the digital transformation process in education. According to statistics, there are 63 educational institutions and 710 education and training departments that have implemented the construction of a common database for education. Currently, 82% of high schools use software for school management. In addition, the adoption of digital transformation has promoted "lifelong learning" and the creation of online materials. For example, there has been the sharing of 5,000 electronic lectures, 7,000 theses, and more than 31,000 multiple-choice questions from expert teachers (Hue et al., 2022). However, digital transformation in education is not simply the use of computers or electronic devices in teaching and learning, it is a complex process, requiring strategic investment, professional knowledge, and commitment from all stakeholders. Therefore, the digital transformation process in education still faces many difficulties:

+ Heterogeneity in access to technology among different types of learners: While in some places, some schools have resources and modern technological infrastructure. In remote areas, it is difficult to access digital technology due to economic conditions and internet problems; Digital document sources still lack quality and content, leading to some information in the search process still lacking accuracy (difficulties in searching). equipping equipment and tools to support learning).

+ Difference and lack of suction: Resources and technological expertise between localities create educational gaps and increase inequality in access to knowledge. Training and development of human resources specialized in technology in education need to be promoted. Teachers need to be trained to use technology effectively in the teaching process and support students in accessing knowledge. In addition, there needs to be investment in developing digital content that is rich and relevant to the curriculum, from basic to advanced levels.

+ Personal information security and network safety issues: With the use of online platforms and applications during the learning process, protecting students' personal information still faces many difficulties and needs to become a priority. As a top priority, it is necessary to develop strong security measures to prevent intrusion and misuse of personal information, as well as ensure cyber safety for students when exposed to online content. .

To address these challenges, close cooperation is needed among stakeholders, from governments, educational organizations, to civil society, to create a sustainable and equitable digital education environment. .

3.3. Digital transformation in education at Thu Dau Mot University

Thu Dau Mot University is a prestigious and good quality university, increasingly recognized and trusted by society. The predecessor of Thu Dau Mot University was Song Be Pedagogical College. In 2009, the school was upgraded to a university with the mission and goal of training quality human resources to serve the socio-economic development and international integration of Binh Duong province, the Southeast region. With continuous development efforts, Thu Dau Mot University has upgraded its reputation and quality to become a multidisciplinary university, with 47 industries university, 11 master's majors, 1 doctoral major, in the fields of economics, engineering and technology, natural sciences, humanities, social sciences, foreign languages, and pedagogy, with a scale of up to 18,000 students (Thu Dau Mot University, 2024). The school builds the core values "Aspiration - Responsibility - Creativity", implements the educational philosophy "Scientific research - Experiential learning - Community service", with a vision to 2030, the school becomes a Smart university with many member schools, ranked 350 in Asia in 2030, learners have the ability to work at home and abroad. Currently, Thu Dau Mot University is a member of CDIO and AUN (Association of Southeast Asian Universities). Having gone through many accreditation cycles of the National Education Quality Accreditation Standards, it has been evaluated well. The school has 20 training majors that meet the quality accreditation standards of the Ministry of Education and Training (MOET), 8 majors that meet AUN-QA standards. In August 2020, the school achieved 4-star UPM (University Performance Metrics) standard. For two consecutive years, the school has been in the top 50 educational institutions with the best international publications in Vietnam (42nd position in 2018 and 27th position in 2019). In 2022, the school ranked 15th on the VNUR ranking of 100 Vietnamese universities. In 2023, the school will enter the Top 5 universities in Vietnam listed on the Schimago rankings. In 2024, the school ranked 18/187 higher education institutions in Vietnam according to Webometrics rankings. To continue promoting its valuable traditions, in the context of society, especially science and technology developing rapidly, Thu Dau Mot University has always paid attention to the field of digital transformation in all activities. of the school. In March 2021, Thu Dau Mot University was trusted by Binh Duong province with the project to build a training course on digital transformation and digital technology for civil servants, workers, students and employees. people in the period 2021 - 2025. This is the premise for the Digital Transformation Training project announced on April 15, 2022. The digital transformation mission and tasks of Thu Dau Mot University include:

+ Digital conversion training for learners

+ Training and consulting on digital transformation for society

Digital Transformation in Education at Thu Dau Mot University

+ Perform internal number conversion.

With that noble task, the project has set the following goals towards 2025:

The goal of implementing the Digital Transformation project at Thu Dau Mot University is until 2025

No	Content	Targets (%)
first	Number of working-age people who know about online public services and basically understand how to use them when needed	70
2	Leaders participate in training and education to raise awareness about digital transformation, digital skills, and digital technology	100
3	Civil servants, public employees and workers in state agencies participate in training to raise awareness about digital transformation, digital skills, and digital technology	60
4	Officers in charge of digital transformation and information technology are trained in digital technology and have their training results evaluated online through the national digital skills standard assessment and testing system.	100
5	Students graduating from fields of technology, engineering, economics, and society are assessed online for their digital skills through the National Digital Skills Standard Assessment and Testing System.	60
6	Teachers who teach subjects in information technology, natural sciences, social sciences, technology, engineering and arts in educational establishments from elementary to high school are trained and fostered in technical skills. STEM/STEAM educational skills, digital skills and online assessment of digital skills through the National Digital Skills Standard Assessment and Testing System	60

Source:(Chi, 2022).

The training program includes 3 levels: basic (mass audience), advanced (professional and operational staff) and intensive (management and strategic level). From June 2022, the school will begin organizing basic level digital conversion training courses and from October 2022 advanced level digital conversion training. The period 2024-2025 will deploy advanced digital transformation courses in the form of package orders, in addition to basic and advanced training courses.

Not only in the project, Argument Transformation is a content that Thu Dau Mot University pays special attention to, expressed through its guiding institutions and activities. Many documents have been issued, such as: Decision No. 372/QĐ – DHTĐM March 27, 2024 of the Principal on the Establishment of a Drafting Team for the project Digital University - Smart University - Happiness at Thu Dau Mot University; Decision No. 20/QĐ - HDTr dated August 13, 2020 of the University Council on promulgating the Plan to implement the Development Strategy of Thu Dau University until 2030 - Information Technology field; Notice No. 54/TB - HDTr on the conclusions of the Chairman of the School Council at the meeting on March 14, 2024; ... These institutional documents are the directions for digital transformation activities at Thu Dau Mot University.

To perform Digital transformation, Thu Dau Mot University has opened many communication channels: through Zalo, through the websites of schools, departments, and centers; look at online learning software, in which elearning is the mainstay; ... Through these communication channels, learners, workers, managers, ... can interact, contact, find information, ... as quickly as possible. In addition to the school's main website, all departments, centers, faculties and members have their own websites, linked to the main school website. Therefore, learners, teachers, information seekers, etc. can easily find the necessary information quickly.

About digital infrastructure: Digital infrastructure is an important basis for implementing digital transformation. Thu Dau Mot University is very interested in investing in digital facilities.

+ Currently, specialized broadband data transmission network infrastructure covers all units, departments, classrooms, etc., ensuring connections to internal applications, such as accessing all websites. departments, institutes, centers, schools; information system for handling administrative procedures; connecting learning, learning materials,...

+ The data center infrastructure is organized into a specialized room, ensuring interconnection and shared applications are operated on this storage infrastructure, such as: public service email system. , document management system, training information system, student registration - cancellation of courses, enrollment, student affairs, ...

+ The school has formed an Internet of Things (IoT) infrastructure to transmit camera data and IoT has been implemented on a large scale throughout the school.

+ Equipment for digital transformation activities has been purchased and installed to achieve the highest efficiency of digital transformation goals. All rooms are equipped with TVs with internet connection to better serve the teaching and learning of teachers and students.

Regarding digital human resources: in addition to 7 members of the Digital Transformation Project Committee, 5 members of the e-learning department, and 6 members of the information technology center play the role of human resources specialized in information technology; All teachers, staff, and workers of the school participate in digital transformation activities. Teachers are the human resources who carry out digital transformation in teaching and connecting with students; Employees and experts of

Digital Transformation in Education at Thu Dau Mot University

departments/departments/centers/institutes are human resources in digital conversion of administrative documents, professional activities, etc. The University owns a team of 744 highly qualified officials and teachers (212 Professors-Associate Professors, 173 PhDs, 487 MScs, 97 PhDs). With a strong and highly qualified workforce, it is a favorable condition for the University to carry out digital transformation in training (Thu Dau Mot University, 2024).

About digital training: TIn each university, the field of training is the most important field, the "soul", the brand that reflects the training quality of each school. In the context of digital transformation, Thu Dau Mot University always focuses on teaching, in which content and methods are the core issues. Equipped with increasingly complete and more modern digital facilities also serve to better serve the innovation of content and methods, to suit society's requirements. Tfollowing the government's direction and directionIn the national digital transformation program, Thu Dau Mot University has taught online courses with at least 20% of the program content, on Elearning online teaching software. At Elearning teaching software, lecturers not only teach lesson content but also design exercises, tests, practice tests... so that students can diversify their learning content and test their proficiency. own. Each e-learning session is recorded by software so students can watch and re-watch and re-learn content they have not yet grasped. On it, lecturers and students can also interact with each other to exchange educational information. Besides, to serve learning and research, the learning resource center also digitizes documents to better serve training. From 2014 up to now, according to statistics from the Learning Resource Center, Thu Dau Mot University has had 26,740 catalogs of digital documents across all disciplines and fields, from social sciences, natural sciences to other fields. engineering, economics, and law; 23,957 digital documents about articles, magazines, theses, etc. Therefore, the training quality of Thu Dau Mot University is increasingly improving, meeting the strict requirements of the labor market in Vietnam. Binh Duong and neighboring provinces.

4. CONCLUDE

With institutions and practical actions in digital transformation, Thu Dau Mot University has achieved many results, quickly transforming all school activities to a new level, better serving learners. , workers. To get those results, it can be seen that the reasons come from:

- The school's leaders have a strategic vision, always have a high sense of responsibility, along with dynamism and a deep awareness of digital transformation.

Elearning interface
Thu Dau Mot University

- A team of teachers who meet and even exceed standards in terms of professional knowledge, with many young teachers with enthusiasm, creativity and passion for the profession.
- School staff are committed to serving and creating favorable conditions for promoting digitalization activities throughout the school system.
- Students show high awareness in the learning and training process, and have autonomy in researching documents, with many students actively participating in scientific research activities.
- Facilities and classrooms are invested and upgraded, equipped with new equipment to ensure the quality of teaching and learning, including a wifi system that covers the entire school, a security camera system and more.

Digital Transformation in Education at Thu Dau Mot University

- Schools provide modern technology equipment and software, such as teacher and student management software, financial management, and many other utilities.
- Training management process, asset management, library, student management, etc. All are digitized.
- The school's information system is deployed through many channels, including website, electronic information page and fanpage. However, besides that There are still limitations:
 - Some officials, lecturers and staff of the University lack enthusiasm, lack of investment in new technology, and lack of creativity in digitalization activities.
 - The technical and information technology service staff is small, so technical errors cannot be promptly corrected during the training process.
 - The internet connection sometimes has poor and intermittent signal.
 - Digital transformation activities are quite new in Vietnam, so many departments have not yet envisioned specific tasks to perform. Forecasting does not have a solid basis, cannot fully measure the risks, and cannot determine the level of success and results that will be achieved.

Therefore, Thu Dau Mot University still needs to continue striving and building and perfecting policy institutions on digital transformation; attract and train core human resources for digital transformation; Encourage lecturers and staff to constantly learn to increasingly perfect their information technology skills, better serving the school's digital transformation. With consensus and joint efforts, Thu Dau Mot University will successfully carry out digital transformation, enhancing its value and reputation in the field of education and training.

REFERENCES

- 1) Aras Bozkurt et al (2015). Distance education research trends: Content analysis of journals 2009-2013. *International review of research on open and distributed learning*. Volume 16, Number 1, February 2015, p. 330–363
- 2) Balyer, A., & Öz, Ö. (2018). Scholars' perspectives on digital transformation in education. *International Journal of Online Education and Teaching (IOJET)*, 5 (4), 809-830. <http://iojet.org/index.php/IOJET/article/view/441/295>
- 3) Phuong Chi (2022). Thu Dau Mot University provides digital transformation training. People's Committee of Binh Duong Province, accessed April 15, 2022, at <https://www.binhduong.gov.vn/thong-tin-tuyen-truyen/2022/04/232-truong-dai-hoc-thu-dau-mot-dao-cao-chuyen-doi-s>.
- 4) Pham Huy Giao (2020). Digital transformation, nature, practice and applications. *Oil and Gas Magazine*, issue 12, 2020, pages 12 - 16.
- 5) Bui Thi Hue et al (2022). Digital transformation in education and training: Current status and solutions. *Vietnam Science and Technology Magazine (electronic page)*. Accessed August 15, 2022, at <https://vjst.vn/vn/Pages/chitiettin.aspx?IDNews=6707&tiende=chuyen-doi-so-trong-traffic-and-dao-cao--thuc-trang-va-giai-phap.aspx>
- 6) Ta Thi Thanh Loan, Dinh Thi Hong Tham (2024). Applying the Kotter model in digital transformation and management of training activities at Thu Dau Mot University. *Proceedings of the conference on Developing postgraduate training activities of Thu Dau Mot University*.
- 7) Nguyen Thi Kim Ngan, 2021. Some remaining issues in the digital transformation process in Vietnam - exchange research. *Scientific Research Journal*. Hanoi Open University 84 (October 2021) 1-9.
- 8) OECD. Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development. (2018). *The future of education and skills: Education 2030*. OECD Education 2030. OECD Publishing, Paris. [http://www.oecd.org/education/2030-project/about/documents/E2030%20Position%20Paper%20\(April 5, 2018\).pdf](http://www.oecd.org/education/2030-project/about/documents/E2030%20Position%20Paper%20(April%205,%202018).pdf)
- 9) OECD. Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development. (2019). *OECD Skills Strategy 2019: Skills to shape a better future*. OECD Publishing, Paris. <https://doi.org/10.1787/9789264313835-en>
- 10) Parlak, B. (2017). Education in the digital age: An analysis of opportunities and practices Süleyman Demirel University. *Journal of the Faculty of Economics and Administrative Sciences*, 22 (15), 1741-1759.
- 11) Peterson, A., Dumont, H., Lafuente, M., Law, N. (2018). Understanding innovative pedagogies: Key themes for analyzing new approaches to teaching and learning. *OECD Education Working Papers*, No. 172. OECD Publishing, Paris. <https://doi.org/10.1787/9f843a6e-en>
- 12) twelfth. Decision No. 749/QĐ-TTg dated June 3, 2020 of the Prime Minister: Approving the "National Digital Transformation Program to 2025, orientation to 2030".
- 13) Decision No. 131/QĐ-TTg dated January 25, 2022 of the Prime Minister: Approving the Project "Strengthening the application of information technology and digital transformation in education and training in the period 2022 - 2025 , oriented to 2030".

Digital Transformation in Education at Thu Dau Mot University

- 14) Schleicher, A. (2016). Teaching excellence through professional learning and policy reform: Lessons from around the world, International Summit on the Teaching Profession, OECD Publishing, Paris.<https://doi.org/10.1787/9789264252059-en>
- 15) Schmarzo, Bill (2017). What is digital transformation?. Accessed at www.cio.com on July 9, 2021.
- 16) Şişman, M. (2016). Introduction to educational science. Publication of the Pegem Academy.
- 17) Thu Dau Mot University. <https://tdmu.edu.vn/>.
- 18) Thomas M. Siebel (translated by Pham Anh Tuan) (2019) Digital transformation. City General Publishing House. Ho Chi Minh.
- 19) WEF. World Economic Forum. (2020). School of the future. Identifying new educational models for the fourth industrial revolution. In Shaping the future of the new economy and society. Cologny/Geneva, Switzerland.http://www3.weforum.org/docs/WEF_Schools_of_the_Future_Report_2019.pdf
- 20) <https://enterpriseproject.com/what-is-digital-transformation>